

YOGIC PRACTICES AND NEUROPSYCHOLOGY: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Background: Yoga is one of the widely used mind-body medicine for health promotion, disease prevention and as a possible treatment modality for neurological disorders. There is a controversy between researcher whether yogic practices improve neuropsychological parameters or not.

Aim: Hence, we performed a comprehensive search in the PubMed/Medline and google electronic database to review relevant articles in English, using keywords “Yoga and Neuropsychology”.

Method: Researchers searched several studies examining the effects of yoga practice on the brain structures, function, and neuropsychological parameters through Pubmed/Medline and other data sources and analysed all the studies according to the nature of the study.

Findings: Related literature supporting the controversies prevailing regarding impact of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters. Some studies reported positive effects on neuropsychological parameters due to yogic practices whereas others group of researchers reported negative or no evidence of positive effects of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters.

Conclusions: This review study concluded that effects of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters is inconclusive and invite further controlled scientific research.

Key Words: Neuropsychology, Yoga, Pranayama, Brain Function, Cognitive Function etc

INTRODUCTION

Neuropsychology is the study of the relationship among brain function, behaviour, and psychological processes. The field of neuropsychology is one which significantly contributing to our knowledge and understanding of the great spellbinder called the brain. Imaging technology, neuropsychological thinking started to gather momentum during the 1950s and 1960s. It was during this era when research and findings from cognitive psychology and brain physiology were integrated into a new field of study. Neuropsychology believes that the brain coordinates many cognitive functions between several brain regions and biochemical processes. The major areas of neuropsychology are memory, perception, coordination, concentration, organization, reasoning etc. Two major research and practice areas define sport neuropsychology in the new millennium :(i) Sport-related concussion and (ii) Neurocognitive/medical well-being. Neuropsychology focuses both on basic research and on applied, clinical research, to stimulate systematic investigation into brain-behaviour relationships and to improve clinical practice. Neuropsychology seeks to communicate the best research and ideas in the field from throughout the world. Several neurological disorders affect mental health and lead to various degrees of impairment in cognitive functions. The use of complementary and alternative medicine, practices that improve the mind’s capacity and body function, amongst patients with neuropsychological disorders is increasing worldwide.

Biofeedback, homeopathy, acupuncture, meditation, and yoga are among the different categories of these interventions. Yoga and pranayama can improve our brain function as well as it helps to developed brain cells, and resulting in improved cognitive skills, such as learning and memory. Yoga strengthens parts of the brain that play a key role in memory, attention, awareness, thought, and language.

Yoga is the most popular complementary health approach practiced by adults in the modern society. It is an ancient mind and body practice with origins in Indian philosophy. Yoga combines physical postures, rhythmic breathing, and meditative exercise to offer the practitioners a unique holistic mind-body experience. While the health benefits of physical exercise are well established, in recent years, the active attentional component of breathing and meditation practice has garnered interest among exercise neuroscientists. Though yoga is one of the widely used mind-body medicine for health promotion, disease prevention and as a possible treatment modality for neurological disorders, there is a lack of evidence-based review. Hence, we performed a comprehensive search in the PubMed/Medline and others electronic database to review relevant articles in English, using keywords” Yoga and Neuropsychology”.

Several neurological disorders affect mental health and lead to various degrees of impairment in cognitive functions. The use of complementary and alternative medicine, practices that improve the mind’s capacity and body function, amongst patients with neuropsychological disorders is increasing worldwide (Erwin Wells R et al. 2011; Mooventhan A et al. 2017). Yoga is a form of mind-body technique that involves and contributes to both mind and body and has been used as a therapeutic intervention in various neurological and psychological disorders (Meyer HB et al. 2012)

There is the controversy and disagreement between the two group of researchers regarding the impact of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters. So many scientific studies have indicated that yogic practices can improve our brain function, although it was not supported by other group. So, to lay down general conclusion and recommendation regarding effects of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters, present researcher search various data sources like Pubmed/Medline, Google scholar, PsycheINFO, EMBASE, J-store etc. During his search, he identified two different groups of research which are categorically stated below:

- 1. Positive Effect of Yogic Practices on Neuropsychological Parameters**
- 2. Negative or No Evidence of Positive Effect of Yogic Practices on Neuropsychological Parameters.**

1.POSITIVE EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS:

Shubhada Talwadkar et al. (2014) evaluated the effect of trataka on cognitive functions of the elderly. Elderly subjects were recruited based on inclusion and exclusion criteria (n = 60). They suggested that trataka can be used as a technique to enhance cognitive function in the elderly peoples. Prashanth Singh et al. (2015) assessed the immediate effect of trataka on cognitive performance using the Stroop color-word test. Performance on the Stroop color-word test was assessed in 30 healthy male volunteers with ages ranging from 18 years to 31 years old (22.57 ± 3.65 years). The participants were tested before and after yogic visual concentration (trataka) and during a control session on two separate days. They concluded that

the trataka technique increased the selective attention, cognitive flexibility, and response inhibition. Peter A Hall et al. (2015) examined the empirical literature on the effects of hatha yoga on executive function (EF). A total of 11 published studies met eligibility criteria: Three studies involved healthy adults, 2 studies involved healthy older adults ($n = 2$), 1 study involved children and adolescents, and 5 studies involved medical ($n = 4$) & forensic ($n = 1$) populations. They concluded that hatha yoga shows promise of benefit for EF in healthy adults, children, adolescents, healthy older adults, impulsive prisoners, and medical populations. better-quality studies are required to evaluate the efficacy of hatha yoga's effects on EF are essential to build on this evidence base. Jingxia Lin et al. (2015) examined whether participating in aerobic exercise or yoga improved cognitive impairments and clinical symptoms. A total of 140 female patients were recruited as subjects of this study. They concluded that both types of exercise improved working memory in early psychosis patients. Neha P Gothe et al. (2015) conducted a study on the effects of yoga on cognitive function. They concluded that Yoga practice seems to be associated with moderate improvements in cognitive function.

Harris A Eyre et al. (2016) conducted a study to explore the relationship between performance on memory tests and resting-state functional connectivity before and after a yoga intervention versus active control for subjects with mild cognitive impairment (MCI). They found that yoga may improve functional connectivity in relation to verbal memory performance. Hemant Bhargav et al. (2016) evaluated immediate effect of two yoga-based relaxation techniques on cognitive functions in patients suffering from relapsing remitting multiple sclerosis. Eighteen subjects (13 females) in the age range of 51.5 ± 12.72 years with the diagnosis of RRMS by a neurologist (McDonald Criteria 2010) were recruited into the study from a neuro-rehabilitation center in Germany. They concluded that Yogic relaxation techniques may have an immediate enhancing effect on processing speed, psychomotor performance, and recall of RRMS patients. Madhusudan Das et al. (2016) investigated the effect of yoga-based intervention on psychomotor performance and self-efficacy in school children. Two hundred ten school children with ages ranging from 11 to 16 years (mean age \pm SD; 13.7 ± 0.8 years) satisfying the inclusion. An equal number of age-matched participants ($n = 210$; mean \pm SD; 13.1 ± 0.8 years) were selected for the control group. They found that yoga practice enhances self-efficacy and processing speed with fine motor coordination, visual-motor integration, visual perception, planning ability, and cognitive performance. Kristi Alexander et al. (2016) investigated the effectiveness of a mindfulness meditation intervention on working memory capacity (WMC) in adolescents. Participants ($N = 198$ adolescents) were recruited from a large public middle school in southwest United States and randomly assigned to mindfulness meditation, hatha yoga, or a waitlist control condition. The result of this study was provided support for the benefits of short-term mindfulness practice, specifically mindfulness meditation, in improving WMC in adolescents. Neha P Gothe et al. (2016) examined whether yoga practice moderated the stress response resulting in improved executive function. After prolonged investigation they concluded that regular yoga practice resulted in improved working memory performance that was mediated by an attenuated response to stress as measured by self-report stress and objective salivary cortisol measurements. Sushil Chandra et al. (2016) analyzed the effects of sudarshan kriya yoga (SKY) on brain signals during a working memory (WM) task. A total of 25 subjects were taken in the study, of which 10 were allotted to a control group and 15 to an experimental group. They found that SKY had shown minimized energy losses while performing the task. SKY can improve WM by changing the brain rhythms such that energy is utilized efficiently in performing the task. Rinku Garg et al. (2016) examined the effect of unilateral right nostril breathing, left nostril breathing and alternate nostril breathing on verbal and spatial memory scores. A total of 51 female subjects (age 18-25 years, mean \pm SD = 21.71 ± 3.11) were taken and divided into three groups

(n=17). They concluded that Inclusion of nostril breathing in exercise regimen may be helpful in improving recall of memory.

Apar Saoji et al. (2017) investigated the effect of a single session of a yogic meditation technique on cognitive performance in medical students. The purpose of this study was to examine the effectiveness of a yogic meditation technique, mind sound resonance technique (MSRT), on cognitive functions of University Medical students, in total, 42 healthy volunteers of both genders (5 males and 37 females) with mean age of 19.44 ± 1.31 years were recruited from a medical college in South India, based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria. A 10-day orientation in the technique of MSRT was given to all the recruited subjects after which each subject underwent both MSRT and supine rest (SR) sessions. They concluded that a single session of MSRT, a Mind-Body Practice, may positively impact the performance in cognitive tasks by the University Medical Students. H G Namratha et al. (2017) evaluated the effect of yoga and working memory training on cognitive communicative abilities among middle aged adults. The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of combining yoga and working memory training among healthy middle-aged adults. A total of 45 participants were randomly assigned into three groups. Group 1 received both yoga and working memory training, group 2 received only working memory training and group 3 served as the control group. They suggest that yoga is not only an alternative approach, but also augmentative in improving cognitive communicative abilities. Sushil Chandra et al. (2017) analyzed the effects of Sudarshan Kriya yoga (SKY) on EEG as well as ECG signals for stress regulation. A total of 20 subjects were taken in this study, of which 10 were allotted to a control group. They suggest that these EEG, ECG and DT shows a significant decrement in mental stress and improvement in cognitive performance after SKY, indicating SKY as a good alternative of medication for stress management. Neha P Gothe et al. (2017) examined the effect of hatha yoga practices on attention and processing speed in older adults. The objective of the study was to evaluate the effects of an 8-week Hatha yoga intervention on attention and processing speed among older adults. Participants (n = 118; mean age, 62 ± 5.59). They found that hatha yoga practice can improve attention and processing speed in older adults. Harris A Eyre et al. (2017) conducted a controlled trial of Kundalini yoga on mild cognitive impairment. The aim of the study is the first to investigate the effects of Kundalini yoga (KY) training on mild cognitive impairment (MCI). They concluded that KY group showed short- and long-term improvements in executive functioning. Savitha Subramaniam et al. (2017) evaluated the effect of yogic practices on reducing cognitive-motor interference for improving dynamic balance control in healthy adults. The objective of the study was to investigate the effects of Yoga on reducing cognitive-motor interference (CMI) for maintaining balance control during varied balance tasks. The outcome of this study suggest that Yoga practice can significantly reduce CMI by improving allocation and utilization of attentional resources for both balance control and cognitive function.

Neha P Gothe et al. (2018) determined the differences in gray matter volume of the hippocampus, thalamus and caudate nucleus and brain activation during the Sternberg working memory task. It is concluded that regular long-term yoga practice and differential structure and function of specific brain regions involved in executive function, specifically working memory, which has previously shown to improve with yoga practice.

Anita David et al. (2019) investigated the effectiveness of yogic visual concentration (Trataka) on cognitive performance and anxiety among adolescents. The objective of the study was to assess the effectiveness of yogic visual concentration (Trataka) on cognitive performance and anxiety among adolescents studying in selected schools at Chennai. They concluded that yogic visual concentration (Trataka) has greater impact on cognitive performance and anxiety among adolescent students. Kankan Gulati et al. (2019) conducted a

study on self-esteem and performance in attentional tasks in school children after 4½ months of yogic practices. 116 children with group mean age $10 \pm$ years were randomly selected as subjects of this study. They suggest that Yoga practice is beneficial for school children as it improves attention, concentration, memory, motor speed, and self-esteem. Satish P Vhavle et al (2019) compared the yogic and physical Exercise group on Executive Function, Attention, and Working Memory in Adolescent School children. They found that yogic practice group improves executive function, attention, and working memory as effectively as physical exercise intervention in adolescent school children.

Stephany Campanelli et al. (2020) examined the effects of Pranayama's on neurophysiological parameters. they concluded that the studies focusing on specific aspects of the practices such as retentions, prolonged expiration, attention on fluid respiration, and abdominal/thoracic respiration should better elucidate the effects of Yogic Breathing Techniques (YBT). Maheshkumar Kuppusamy et al. (2020) examined the effect of Bhramari pranayama practice on simple reaction time in healthy adolescents. Total 730 potential subjects screened, 520 apparently healthy adolescents randomly assigned to either the experimental group (n-260) or control group (n-260). Experimental group practiced the bhramari pranayama for 3 days in a week for 6 months. They reported that the beneficial effect of bhramari pranayama on reaction time can be used for improving cognitive function in the adolescents for their academic performances. Shibaji Chobe et al. (2020) investigated the effects of yoga and ayurveda rasayana combined intervention on cognition among the elderly with mild cognitive impairment. Total 72 elderly persons (average age 63.3 ± 6.44 years) received ayurveda rasayana (AR) (n = 23) or Integrated Yoga (IY) (n = 25) or combined (IY plus AR) intervention (n = 24) for eight weeks. They found that both ayurveda rasayana and yoga intervention significantly improved learning, attention, processing speed, and working memory compared to individual response among elderly persons with MCI. Corina Moller et al (2020) conducted a study on short-term mindfulness program on memory performance in school-aged children. They concluded that the regular meditative practice improves cognitive functions in childhood and it also shows that school-aged children can benefited from short-term meditation programs. Louis-Nascan Gill et al. (2020) have done a meta-analytical study on mindfulness induction and cognition. They found that mindfulness induction improves cognitive performance. U S Anusuya et al. (2020) conducted a study on effect of mind sound resonance technique (A yoga-based relaxation technique) on psychological variables and cognition in school children. Total 60 students with age ranging between 14-16 years (mean age \pm SD; 15.3 ± 0.71 years) were randomly selected as subjects of this study. They suggest that the current trial indicate the beneficial role of MSRT in enhancing psychological and cognitive functions in children. Shivaji Chobe et al. (2020) reviewed several studies related to the impact of yoga on cognition and mental health among elderly. They concluded that Yoga-based interventions have some positive evidence in improving attention, executive functions, and memory of cognition.

Sara Hoy et al. (2021) reviewed the effects of yoga-based interventions on cognitive function in healthy older adults: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials. Total 1466 records were initially identified; six studies (5 unique trials) were included in the review. They reported that Yoga-based interventions are associated with improvements in cognition in healthy older adults. Sridip Chatterjee et al. (2021) examined the Effect of 12 Weeks of Yogic Training on Neurocognitive Variables: A Quasi-Experimental Study. The aim of the study was to evaluate the effect of 12 weeks of yogic training on neurocognitive abilities in a middle-aged group. A total of 86 volunteers (46 male and 40 females, age group of 35-55 years), with no prior experience of yoga were participated in this study. All participants divided

into yoga training group (male = 21 and female = 18) and control group (male = 20 and female = 18). The yoga training group underwent yoga practices, including *kriya*, *surya namaskar*, *asana*, *pranayama*, and *dhyana* daily in the morning. They concluded that Integrated approach of yogic intervention may have promising effect on neurocognitive abilities that concomitantly promote successful aging. P S Swathi et al. (2021) investigated the effect of *trataka* (Yogic Visual Concentration) on the Performance in the Corsi-Block Tapping Task. The present study was planned to assess the immediate effects of *trataka* and of eye exercise sessions on the Corsi-block tapping task (CBTT). A total of 41 healthy volunteers of both genders with age 23.21 ± 2.81 years were recruited. All participants underwent baseline assessment, followed by 2 weeks of training in *trataka* (including eye exercise). Each training session lasted for 20 min/day for 6 days a week. They concluded that *trataka* session improves working memory, spatial memory, and spatial attention. Kallol Kumar Bhattacharyya et al. (2021) evaluated the effects of yoga-related mind-body therapies on cognitive function in older adults: A systematic review with meta-analysis. They found that yoga can be a useful part of daily routine to maintain cognitive function in older adulthood.

Asma Aloui et al. (2022) conducted a study on effects of hatha yoga on cognitive functions in the elderly: a cross-sectional study. The purpose of the study was to investigate the effects of hatha yoga practice on cognitive functions in the elderly. Total 30 healthy older men participated in this study. They belonged to two groups. The first group included 15 hatha yoga practitioners for at least two years. The control group involved 15 male older adults who shared the same characteristics as the hatha yoga group but were naive to yoga, meditation, or any mind-body intervention. They have concluded that long-term hatha yoga practitioners have better cognitive abilities compared to the control group in certain aspects of cognitive functions. Lavya Shetty et al. (2022) wrote an article on effects of yoga on cognitive functions among adolescents. They concluded that Yoga training improves cognitive functions and is a simple, low-cost, and effective adjuvant modality. Sigal Eialt- Adar et al. (2022) reviewed several studies related to influence of yoga on the cognitive function of people aged 60 years and older. They concluded that yoga may offer benefits to cognitive function with a larger number of participants and rigorous research methods are required to support this recommendation. Niranjana Parajuli et al. (2022) investigated the effect of yoga on cognitive functions and anxiety among female school children with low academic performance. They concluded that Yoga improves general intelligence, visuospatial working memory, and attention, as well as reduces the anxiety of students with low academic performance. Kaberi Ghosh et al. (2023) evaluated immediate practice effect of *vrikshasana* on neurocognitive components. They concluded that selected neurocognitive components are increased after immediate practice of *vrikshasana*. Naveen G Halappa et al. (2023) suggested that yoga may be integrated with sports to enhance neurocognitive functions. Aravind Sathya et al (2024) examined a controlled trial with a parallel-arm design to evaluate the effects of a 4-week Surya Nadi pranayama (SNP) on cognition among schoolchildren. The findings of this research may contribute to the development of interventions aimed at improving cognitive functioning in school-aged children after 4-week specific yogic breathing techniques. Gurudutta Gangenahalli et al. (2024) conducted a study on effects of *Yoga* and *Pranayama* on the overall development of the body including neurocognitive function. They identified that *Yoga* can also help in improving the neurophysiological, neurophysiological, and neurocognitive function of the brain.

2. NEGATIVE OR NO EVIDENCE OF POSITIVE EFFECT OF YOGIC PRACTICES ON NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL PARAMETERS:

While yoga practice may exert various physical and psychological health benefits, there are some reports on its adverse effects. Yoga training may transiently increase the intraocular pressure and lead to progressive optic neuropathy, particularly in patients with glaucoma, [de Barros DS et al. (2008)]. Moreover, there are several reports of peripheral nerve injuries after a yoga practice, particularly in the elderly subjects who take sedative medications and patients with hypermobility of the connective tissue, Baute V (2019) and Walker M (2005).

Balaram Pradhan et al. (2013) examined the effect of breathing exercise, Kapalabhati (KB), on psychomotor performance, as measured by the six-letter cancellation task (SLCT) and digit-letter substitution task (DLST). Total 60 subjects, 21 male (mean age 25.71 years, SD 2.10), 15 female (mean age 24.13 years, SD 2.23) were participated in this study. They found that no changes on both SLCT and DLST. But, this kind of breathing practices leads to increases error score. Neha P Gothe et al. (2014) examined movement-based embodied contemplative practices such as yoga and their effects on cognition. The purpose of this randomized controlled trial was to examine the effects of an 8-week hatha yoga intervention on executive function. They concluded that results demand larger systematic trials to thoroughly examine effects of yoga on executive function as well as across other domains of cognition, and its potential to maintain or improve cognitive functioning in the aging process. Philip David Zelazo et al. (2018) investigated the effects of mindfulness Plus Reflection Training on executive function in early childhood. They suggest that a brief, small-group, school-based intervention teaching mindfulness and reflection did not improve executive function.

Ashwin Kamath et al. (2020) determined the effect of unilateral left nostril breathing (ULNB) on nonlateralized, overall cognitive functions using computerized psychometric tests. Total 20 healthy yoga-naïve medical students. ULNB was performed for 15 min by the test group (n = 10) and breath awareness by the control group (n = 10). The result of this study showed no difference in the effects of 15-min practice of ULNB and breath awareness on cognitive functions; both improved memory but not attention or executive function. Rima Solianik et al. (2020) investigated the effect of yoga on cognitive and motor functioning in older adults. Participants aged 60-79 years were randomized to either a control group (n = 15) or a yoga group (n = 18) for a 10-week period. The yoga group received 90-min duration yoga classes two times per week. They found that 10 weeks of yoga practice resulted in improved balance and learning in the speed-accuracy motor task that were mediated by increased BDNF levels, but had no impact on cognition in older adults. Borko Katanic et al. (2021) investigated the effects of a 12 weeks yoga intervention program on motor and cognitive abilities in preschool children. They concluded that preschool yoga intervention significantly improved their motor abilities, but not their cognitive abilities. Marlon Danilewitz et al. (2021) explored the combination of transcranial direct stimulation and yoga. Twenty-two healthy volunteers with a regular yoga practice were randomized to receive either active transcranial direct stimulation followed by yoga intervention or sham transcranial direct stimulation followed by yoga intervention a double-blind, cross-over design over two separate intervention days. They suggest that there was no significant difference between active versus sham transcranial direct stimulation concerning working memory performance and mindfulness, which may be accounted by the small sample size, the transient nature of the intervention. Geneva Millett et al. (2021) reviewed several scientific studies which is related to mindfulness meditation programs and executive functioning. The objective of this study was to critically analyzed all

the studies carefully. They found that the effect of group-based mindfulness training on executive functioning is not robust. No significant pooled effects were found for attention shifting.

CONCLUSION:

Most scientific publications on yoga deal with the efficacy of said programs to gain an understanding of the subject to counsel patients appropriately. However, the usefulness of meditation specifically for clinicians, as an occupation group that is particularly associated with physical and mental health risks, still needs more accurate evidence. Although most investigations are in Favor of the beneficial effects of yoga on neuropsychological disorders, some studies have not found this meditative procedure useful.

Several points in the studies that have shown the beneficial impacts of yoga on neuropsychological disorders have to be taken into consideration. Multiple investigations reporting beneficial effects of yoga on neuropsychological disorders were not precise in design, implementation, and analysis. There was considerable heterogeneity among the description of yoga interventions in different studies. Different yoga types and many disciplines within the practice have been conducted with various duration and frequency of training. Furthermore, many of these studies have several limitations, such as small sample sizes, short-term follow-up, confounding variables, and lack of appropriate controls.

Impact of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters or more specifically effect of yogic practices on brain function is an area of controversy. One group who concluded that there is no such positive effect of yogic practices on neuropsychological functions. Whereas other group who supported that there are some positive effects of yogic practices on neuropsychological function or brain function. Effects of yogic practices on neuropsychological parameters is still now inconclusive and further in-depth scientific study is recommended.

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